

I am in support of the passing of the LGBTQ bill in our nation. As Christian Nation we do not want to incur the wrath of God upon our nation and therefore we will not compromise our Godly values to any oppressor or oppressors. Thank you. God richly bless you for the good works you are doing for mother Ghana. Amen!

I S██████ A██████ D██████ support the passing of the whole Bill FOR The Promotion Of Proper Human Sexual Right and Ghanaian Family Values. on the basis of the fact that,

1) The Scripture and for that matter God the creator Himself is against the activities of the LGBTQ+ and so He supports this Bill.

2) Nature itself supports this Bill

3) Our Culture supports this Bill

4) Even all our three (3) Major Religions in Ghana:- Christianity, Islamic and Traditional Religions supports this Bill.

I therefore pray the Parliament of Ghana to consider the above reasons in order not to incur the wrath of God upon this nation but pass this Bill for the betterment of Ghana.

Thank you.